

UZBEKISTAN AS A SOCIAL STATE: REFORMS AND PROMISING DIRECTIONS IN THE SOCIAL SPHERE

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Uzbekistan is located at the crossroads of cultures and civilizations, having shaped its social structure over centuries through unique traditions and values. In the era of globalization and rapid development of the market economy, Uzbekistan's primary strategic aim – the construction of a social state is reflected in the first article of the new version of the Constitution. According to the principles of a welfare state, a range of measures to strengthen the country's social protection system and expand the volume of social services provided to citizens have been implemented.

In particular, large-scale reforms are being carried out to improve the well-being of the population by ensuring employment and increasing incomes, reducing unemployment and poverty. For instance, a system of support for families, women, and youth in need of social assistance has been established across the country through programs such as the "Unified social protection register", "Temir daftar", "Ayollar daftari", "Yoshlar daftari" and "Mahallabay".

It should be noted that as part of the social reforms being carried out in Uzbekistan, preschool education coverage is increasing. As of January 2024, more than 2 million children aged 3-7 or 74 percent, are enrolled in primary education. The priority goal is to increase this figure to 80 percent by 2026 and to 100 percent by 2030. At the same time, against the backdrop of a 2.5-fold increase in enrollment of higher education institutions, their number has reached 213. This has created a foundation for increasing the level of higher education coverage from 38 to 42 percent compared to 2022. In the healthcare sector, the full implementation of the "State medical insurance" system in Tashkent city and Syrdarya region by the end of 2024 reflects a characteristic feature of developed social states in government policy.

In addition, with the aim of supporting the younger generation and providing them with employment, 5.2 thousand young people are being trained in IT professions within the framework of the projects "Future Skills Uzbekistan" and "Bir million dasturchi", while 6.4 thousand women are acquiring entrepreneurial skills through the projects "Yoshlar 1+1" and "Tadbirkor ayol". Within the "Ishga marhamat" and "Monocenter" systems, young people and women are being trained in 30 different professions and gradually provided with employment¹.

¹ https://uzbekembassy.com.my/uzb/news_press/jamiyat/ozbekiston_ijtimoiy_davlat.html

It is known that the development of the first modern welfare state began about 125 years ago with the development of state social security systems in Western Europe. In particular, in conservative countries such as Germany, France, and Austria, social insurance benefits play a significant role. Therefore, in these countries, financial claims are closely tied to wages. Scandinavian countries, such as Sweden, Norway, Denmark, and Finland, in contrast to the insurance system, have a system of high taxes that benefit the public based on civil rights. However, in liberal countries such as the United States, Great Britain, Australia, and Chile, social policy emphasizes the free market and the family. If we look at the history of modern ideal welfare states, we see that they adhere to one of three major models that existed previously, and whose theoretical foundations have been confirmed. Table 1 presents models of the welfare state².

Table 1

Comparative analysis of social state models

Regime Type	Liberal	Conservative	Social Democratic
Central Regulatory Idea	Individual Responsibility	Status-Hierarchy	Universalism
Decommodification (= Protection against dependence from the labor Market)	Minimal	High (for "breadwinner")	Maximum
Dominant Principle of the Social Security System	Care	Insurance	Provision
Dominant Value Orientation	Freedom	Security	Equality
Essential Social Structuring Effect	Exclusion	Segmentation	Inclusion
Country Groups	Anglo-Saxon Countries	Continental European Countries	Scandinavian Countries
Assigned Countries	USA, Australia, Great Britain, Switzerland, Japan	Germany, Austria, France, Belgium	Sweden, Norway, Denmark, Finland, Netherlands

However, the criteria for an ideal welfare state are difficult to express in exact numerical terms, as such indicators vary between states and countries. These indicators can also change over time. Therefore, a prosperous state is a

² Bodo L. "Klare Mehrheiten für den Wohlfahrtsstaat\Gesellschaftliche Wertorientierungen im internationalen Vergleich", Bonn, 2008, S-7.

comprehensive concept, and modern scientific literature notes the presence of its five important pillars. It means that certain social services and citizens' rights should be financed from general tax revenues. Below, in table 2, the list of the primary social services of a prosperous state is presented³.

Table 2

Education	at least primary and secondary education
Health care	health care access for all, in terms of services and funding mechanisms
Social protection	of social welfare and social security financed by tax-funded social assistance
Labor market	active labor market policies to generate employment, as well as microcredit and insurance provisions for the enterprise sector
Family policy	such as child-related policies and welfare services

Main social spheres in the social state

According to the table above, Uzbekistan is also conducting significant reforms in primary, secondary, and secondary specialized education as part of its social state system. In particular, as a result of these reforms, in the 2022-2023 academic year, 100 billion sums were allocated from the state budget for free meals for primary school students in the Republic of Karakalpakstan and Khorezm Region. In the near future, it is planned to introduce this positive practice in all schools in other regions and the city of Tashkent.

Also, within the framework of the “Uzbekistan-2030” Strategy, the education system occupies a special place as a key goal for the development of New Uzbekistan. By 2030, it is planned to establish free buses for students of 715 secondary schools located in remote and out-of-the-way areas, fully provide them with clean drinking water and modern sanitary and hygienic infrastructure. In addition, by 2026, the share of qualified teachers with higher education in schools will be increased from 81.8 to 87.8 percent. To ensure the quality of education for children with disabilities, there are 90 specialized schools and boarding schools in the republic, where 21,447 children study.

In recent years, Uzbekistan has set a goal of further developing the health care sector and achieving 100% digitalization of medical institutions. In particular, in August 2022, Uzbekistan and the German bank KfW signed a loan agreement for 45 million euros and a grant agreement for 5.5 million euros for the “Support for digital health reforms” project. According to the agreement, a plan of measures for the digitalization of the healthcare system in 2023-2025 was approved, and the

³ Köhler G., Is There an “Asian Welfare State Model?”, East and South Asian Trajectories and Approaches to the Welfare State, organized by the Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung (FES) in Tutzing, Germany, 2014.

development of the “Elektron retsept” (reimbursement), “Elektron sanatoriya” and “Cancer-registr” platforms was planned. Currently, the “Elektron poliklinika” and “Elektron shifoxona” systems have been launched in many regions of the republic, and a mechanism has been established to provide access to quality medical services for all⁴.

At the same time, it is important to double the amount of funds allocated to the country's healthcare system and to widely attract foreign investment. In particular, in the first quarter of 2024, the volume of healthcare services amounted to 2250.4 billion sums, and we see that the total volume of services in the sector has increased by 1.8 percent. This means that compared to the corresponding period of 2023, the growth rate of services reached 114.2 percent.

It should be noted that Uzbekistan pays special attention to supporting vulnerable segments of the population by expanding social protection programs and digitalizing them. According to him, the funds allocated to social protection programs have increased significantly. As a result of the reforms carried out in the field, it is also planned to increase the income of more than 4 million people who are at risk of poverty in the country.

In particular, in order to provide quality social services and assistance to the population, in accordance with the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 1, 2023, the “National agency for social protection” was established, which has been assigned a number of tasks. An information platform “Unified register of social protection” has been introduced under the Agency, which is a system for the transparent and effective implementation of targeted state support for the needy part of the population. In order to improve the living conditions of citizens included in this register, the “State social protection fund” has been launched. The fund's activities consist in directly assisting 30 categories of the population in need of social protection in finding their place in society.

Uzbekistan is also paying special attention to further improving the employment system and the labor market. In particular, as of January 2024, employment and labor market indicators in the Republic of Uzbekistan showed positive growth, along with a decrease in the unemployment rate, new jobs were created. In order to improve the mechanisms for including low-income, vulnerable segments of the population in the social assistance system and expanding their participation in the labor market, the organizations under the Ministry of Employment and Poverty Reduction have introduced a program to promote the employment of more than 180 thousand people with disabilities in permanent jobs. The republic plans to take measures to employ people from socially vulnerable groups in reserve (quota) jobs and attract 50.2 thousand unemployed citizens to paid public works. At the same time, measures are being

⁴ <https://www.spot.uz/oz/2023/05/02/healthcare-system/>

taken to provide subsidies to the unemployed and employers to stimulate employment.

Moreover, Uzbekistan, as a social state, is positively addressing issues related to families in society, ensuring the well-being of the population and strengthening social protection. As a result of fruitful work in this area in recent years, 250 thousand young families have been provided with new housing. 45 thousand young families with low incomes have been provided with subsidies of 2.4 trillion sums for a down payment and interest payments. Also, 85 thousand houses have been built for low-income families, and mortgage loans of 17 trillion sums have been allocated⁵.

A key priority in building a prosperous state in Uzbekistan is the social protection of children. In particular, young people make up more than 55 percent of our country's population. This is important for ensuring the rights of children in the country and creating the necessary opportunities for them. Therefore, today, based on the needs and desires of children, entertainment venues, IT parks, and "Children's creative unions" have been created in all regional and district centers of the republic. These created opportunities are part of the effective work aimed at raising a healthy generation.

In conclusion, Uzbekistan as a social state is taking consistent measures to ensure the well-being of the population and strengthen social protection. The funds allocated to the social sphere in our country make up a significant portion of the state budget. This will ensure the well-being of the country and the achievement of high indicators in such areas as education, healthcare, social protection, and employment. All reforms carried out within the framework of the social state program are aimed at improving the living standards of citizens and creating all the conveniences necessary for their prosperous life based on the principle of "Person, society, state".

⁵ <https://parliament.gov.uz/articles/2062>

